

Introduction to Optical Access Nodes – power consumption and energy saving study

An answer to Potential Study Items #2 of “IOWN GF for Energy Usage/Efficiency Improvement Proposal” by Gary Li

Michał Szymański, Geraldine Calvignac (Orange)

IOWN GF 6th MM, Septembre 2023

IOWN
GLOBAL FORUM

“IOWN GF for Energy Usage/Efficiency Improvement Proposal” by Gary Li

Potential Study Items #2:

There are various power saving features (e.g., sleep modes, P state, C state) in mobile networks and data center. However, there has been no summary of power saving features in Open APN.

- This proposal is to **conduct a study to summarize what is the current state of power saving features that can be developed for APN networks**, such as in APN-T, APN-G, and APN-I, and other network controllers.

Optical Access Nodes – power consumption and energy saving study

1. Study of main energy consumption factor in OLT
2. Current state of energy-saving features for OLT-ONU
3. Mapping to APN-T, APN-G and APN-I,
referring to « All photonic Central Office” presentation by P. Chanclou at IOWN On-site Workshop 2023.02.06-08, Paris: proposed evolution scenarios of OLT functional architectures towards photonic integration
4. Lessons learned from feature development in Orange

Fixed Access Node: OLT power consumption

